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Research Article

**EVALUATION OF VOLATILE ORGANIC COMPOUNDS IN
THE DIAGNOSIS OF SEXUALLY TRANSMITTED
INFECTIONS USING THE PIEZOQUARTZ MICRO-
WEIGHING METHOD.**

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Article Received: January 2020 **Accepted:** February 2020 **Published:** March 2020**Abstract:**

In recent years, there has been an obvious and regular evolution of the etiological structure of severe infections in obstetrics and gynecology, associated with changes in the premorbid background of patients, the presence of complex hormonal disorders, chronic extragenital diseases, an increase in the number of immunocompromised patients, and, no less important, the expansion of the volume and nature of invasive medical interventions, widely and uncontrolled antibiotic therapy.

Currently, there are various methods for diagnosing sexual infections: native and colored smear bacterioscopy, culture, serological (ELISA), DNA diagnostic (PCR), and the femoflor test system, which differ in sensitivity, ease of use, accessibility, and price. The correct choice of diagnostic method is very important, because various infections require reliable detection of "their" method and tests. The experience of STI treatment shows that the appointment of diagnostic measures and necessary tests to detect the disease requires an individual approach.

Goal: Investigate volatile organic compounds of various classes that are characteristic of a certain type of sexually transmitted infections.

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ANNOTATION:

In recent years, there has been an obvious and regular evolution of the etiological structure of severe infections in obstetrics and gynecology, associated with changes in the premorbid background of patients, the presence of complex hormonal disorders, chronic extragenital diseases, an increase in the number of immunocompromised patients, and, no less important, the expansion of the volume and nature of invasive medical interventions, widely and uncontrolled antibiotic therapy.

Currently, there are various methods for diagnosing sexual infections: native and colored smear bacterioscopy, culture, serological (ELISA), DNA diagnostic (PCR), and the femoflor test system, which differ in sensitivity, ease of use, accessibility, and price. The correct choice of diagnostic method is very important, because various infections require reliable detection of "their" method and tests. The experience of STI treatment shows that the appointment of diagnostic measures and necessary tests to detect the disease requires an individual approach.

Goal:

Investigate volatile organic compounds of various classes that are characteristic of a certain type of sexually transmitted infections.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

The study included 54 patients. All were examined clinically, specific examination for the presence of bacterial and / or viral infection was carried out using microscopic methods, PCR, ELISA.

The patients were divided into two groups: "main" with STIs and "clinically healthy" who did not have sexually transmitted infections during physical, clinical and laboratory examination. 16 (29.6%) people from the "main group" were diagnosed with chlamydia infection, 13 people (24%) -Ureaplasma infection, 7 people (12.9%)- candidiasis, 8 people

(14.8%)-HPV. "Clinically healthy" accounted for 10 people (18.5 per cent).

In order to improve diagnostics, a method of rapid diagnostics of the presence of a certain type of sexually transmitted infections is proposed, which consists in the qualitative determination of volatile organic compounds in bioassays.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

A special feature of the method of analysis of bioassays using the gas analyzer "Aqua Stok" is the ability to obtain analytical information of different levels of differentiation (generalization) based on the results of a single analysis.

The computer program of the gas analyzer not only saves the original, most complete information about the measurement, but also allows you to process it with increasing complexity of the algorithms used. The database obtained during measurement can be transferred to another program and processed using modern methods of chemometry, which allow you to get the maximum information about the object.

The method of piezoquartz microweighting is based on selective absorption of STI marker gases by thin films with highly specific modifiers of piezoquartz resonators (PCR). The primary task is to select modifier films for an array of piezosensors that are highly sensitive to gas markers of normal and pathogenic microflora. To correctly select the modifier films and train the array of piezosensors, the following test substances were selected for STI diagnostics as marker gases: triethylamine, dimethylformamide of dimethyl acetal, cyclohexylamine, piperidine, benzylamine, aniline, methylaniline, acetic acid, butyric acid, ammonia, and-as the main interfering component-water. These compounds are similar in properties to marker gases, since they are products of bacterial activity at certain stages of their life cycle, or when interacting with the flora of the vagina and cervical canal. Some characteristics of the selected test substances are shown in table. 1

Table 1: Some physical and chemical characteristics of test substances

Sorbates	structural formula	M_r^* , a.e.m.	T_k , °C	C^{**} , мг/м ³	pK_a
Triethylamine (TEA)		101,2	89,5	22,21	10,87
Dimethylformamide Of Dimethyl Acetal (DMA DMFA)		119,04	80,93	1,52	-
Piperidine (P)		85,16	106,17	8,30	11,25
Cyclohexylamine (October)		99,18	134	3,39	-
Aniline (But)		93,14	184,4	0,20	4,72
N-Methylaniline (N-MA)		107,16	195,7	0,16	4,85
Benzylamine (BAH)		107,16	184,5	0,26	9,37
Ammonia (AM) NH3	NH_3	17	-33,35	0,95	9,25
Acetic acid (UK)	CH_3COOH	60,05	117,8	0,19	4,76
Butyric Acid (MK)	$CH_3(CH_2)_2COOH$	88,1	163	0,40	4,82

M_r^* – Is the molecular mass expressed in atomic units of mass (a. e. m.)

C^{**} – Concentration of test substance vapors in the detection cell, mg / m³

Kinetic "visual prints»

a)

"Visual prints» maxima's

максимумов
 $\Delta F, \Gamma\zeta$

б)

"Candidiasis", SW.o= 711 Hz * s

a)

б)

Ureaplasmosis, SW.o= 685 Hz * s

a)

б)

Chlamydia, SW.o= 371 Hz * s

"Human papillomavirus" ("HPV"), SW.σ= 1090 Hz * s

The main group is characterized by different "visual impressions" of the responses of the array of sensors in the RGF above the bioassays, not only corresponding to different diseases, but also within the group for a single disease. This may be due to the increased influence of the bioprobe matrix on the composition of the RGF, since the same disease can cause various disorders in the microflora of the cervical canal, so that the differences between the "visual prints" over the biopsies for STIs are leveled, which makes it difficult to determine the type of pathogen.

It was found that the features of the composition of RGF over samples with different types of pathogens are manifested in the sorption kinetics on polar sensors and allow clearly and reliably classifying them into the groups "ureaplasmosis", "chlamydia", "candidiasis", "HPV".

Based on the features of the form of kinetic "visual prints" and the most easily evaluated quantitative criteria for sorption of substances from the RPF, it is possible to rank samples by selected groups of infectious agents with a clear difference between their group "clinically healthy" and the presence of diagnostic criteria for the pathogen.

Thus, without the use of complex algorithms, early, rapid identification of the type of pathogen of sexually transmitted infection is possible, the state of the bioprobe from the cervical canal is assessed with an unambiguous diagnostic parameter "clinically healthy" and patients distributed by type of infection.

To obtain the maximum diagnostic information, it is necessary to use modern methods of processing multiparametric information (Chemometrics), among which the most common is the main component method.

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